

PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF THE SOCIAL LICENSE TO OPERATE IN FOUR EUROPEAN LITHIUM PROJECTS

by

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Lithium is needed for green energy transition, and it is produced outside of European Union (EU). However, EU has promising lithium projects, but such as regarding mining and mineral exploration in general, their local acceptance may be important for their viability (Graham et al. 2021). Europe has a record of mining-related disputes (Kivinen et al. 2020, Lesser 2021), and the recent obstruction of the Jadar Valley lithium project in Serbia by the government is an example of the importance of the social license to operate (SLO) also for the green energy transition (De Layne et al. 2022). SLO means acceptance or approval of a project by the local community or society (Thomson & Boutilier 2011).

Four European lithium projects are preliminary assessed regarding their acceptance and possible disputes: Rapasaari and Syväjärvi in Kaustinen (hereby referred as Kaustinen) in Finland, St. Austell in Great Britain, Beauvoir in France and Mina do Barroso in Portugal (Fig. 1). For this purpose, a literature and online media report search and review were carried out. Search was carried out by a simple Google query using company and project names as keywords. This procedure based on protest event analysis (PEA; Koopmans & Ruch 1999) is an appropriate first and remote approach to detect any local disagreements regarding the projects. According to Earl et al. (2004), opposition needs media attention for its protest and demands and online media reports are available and useful for that purpose. In addition, corporate websites of the companies in question were also checked to see which community relationship strategies they communicate online following the methodology described by Eerola (2021). The projects are case studies of the Horizon Europe Project EXCEED (“Cost-effective, sustainable and responsible extraction routes or recovering distinct critical metals and industrial minerals as by-products from key European hard-rock lithium projects”, Grant Agreements no. 101091543). The mentioned projects aim for lithium production from pegmatites/granites/kaolin.

Fig. 1. Location of the four case studies.

The Rapasaari and Syväjärvi projects owned by Stillwater-Siboney Keliber Oy are in Kaustinen, western Finland (Figs, 1, 2). The company aims to start production from pegmatites in 2024. The region has no mining-related disputes, but the mine sites are close to Natura 2000 area (Fig. 2). Eerola (2021) shown that the Keliber was one of the twenty companies operating in Finland that employed and communicated online about its SLO-related strategies.

Figure 2. The Kaustinen lithium project in western Finland.

The Mina do Barroso project is owned by Savannah Resources in northern Portugal. Production would be from LCT-pegmatite ores. At the end of May 2023, the Portuguese authorities approved the environmental impact assessment (EIA) for the Mina do Barroso spodumene mine project (Silva 2023).

The Trevalour project in St. Austell, Cornwall, UK, is operated by Cornish Lithium plc. It is in an old mining heritage area and the project is in exploration stage. The company aims to produce lithium from granite/kaolin and thermal water.

The Emili project in Beauvoir (Allier), western France is owned by Imerys Minerals Ltd. It is planned to start production from granite in 2028.

Based on the corporate websites, all companies practice active stakeholder engagement and communication in order to maintain a good company-community relationship. The Keliber's project was not among the twenty cases of mining-related disputes mapped in Finland by Eerola (2022), but environmental concerns regarding the Kaustinen project have been expressed by local non-governmental organizations and landowner and fishery associations (Vihanta 2019). They appealed against the permit approval, but it was in great part rejected by the Supreme Court ruling (Holopainen 2021). Except of the Mina do Barroso, there seems to not have any open resistance towards the projects and quite positive picture is given for all other projects in the media. Beyond other mining-related disputes in Portugal (see Chaves 2021, Domingues 2022), Mina do Barroso is also the only project with critical academic articles on it (e.g., Dunlap & Riquito 2023).

Further steps would be to study the associated land use and the sites in more detail regarding the project location in potentially sensitive contexts.

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